

Annihilation in the Gluon Dominance Model

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Physicists carry out experiments at modern accelerators with constantly increasing energy to find out new phenomena and approaches to understanding of internal hadron structure and also answer many questions emerged before them. These experiments agree well on the modern theory of strong interactions, quantum chromodynamics, but there are some results in cosmological observations that can not be explained in this theory and thus require new approaches and experiments. In that way the increasing of measurement precision and rare event registration, building of other theoretical models and just to name a few can help. Also we think that more detailed analysis of the known interactions can make more clear the structure of the matter. Multiparticle production is one of such studies in high energy physics. We offer a single view to describe annihilation processes of leptons and hadrons. It is based on both QCD quark-gluon jets and phenomenological description of hadronization.

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1. Introduction

Active study of multiparticle production (MP) began in the far seventies. Energies of accelerators allowed to find out new particles. By that time the proton, the pion, the electron, their antiparticles and strange ones were known. To explain their MP, the different phenomenological models were proposed [1–3].

Accelerative experiments led to appearance of the modern theory of strong interactions, quantum chromodynamics (QCD). Up to now, it remains consistent with data in the

perturbation (P) region [4]. To describe data in the non perturbation (NP) region different phenomenological models and Monte Carlo generators are applied.

Study of multiparticle processes helps us to understand deeper the NP region of QCD by looking at the mechanism of formation of secondaries through phenomenological models. Our gluon dominance model [5–8] allows us to describe basic multiparticle interactions. We divide them into a few groups:

- electron-positron annihilation (e^+e^-);
- proton-proton interactions ($p\bar{p}$);
- three-gluon decay of quarkonium (Υ);
- proton-antiproton annihilation ($p\bar{p}$).

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- lepton-hadron interaction (ep).

Almost all of them are united by the single approach to describe the multiplicity distributions (MD). It is based on two stages of MP. The first stage represents the development of a quark-gluon cascade. It can include gluon fission and/or bremsstrahlung of quarks. These elementary events are described by PQCD [9, 10].

We started learning MP from e^+e^- annihilation and called our scheme the two stage model [5]. Then, when we applied it to proton interactions and we changed its name to the gluon dominance model (GDM) [6, 7]. It is related to the important properties that we found out for MP: passivity of valence quarks and the active role of gluons as sources of secondaries.

It is important to stress that our future experiment at the SPD setup is dedicated to the study of the gluon component in nucleons [11]. The future electron-ion collider at BNL center states in front of the physical community the same question: “Gluons are carriers of the strong force, bind quarks together inside nucleons and nuclei and generate nearly all of the visible mass in the Universe. Despite their importance, fundamental questions remain about the role of gluons in nucleon and nuclei” [12].

Simultaneously, we described MD of hadrons for the decay of a heavy quarkonium (Υ) considering it as the three-gluon branching [13]. It is necessary to note that we describe hadronization for all listed multiparticle processes by the universal scheme. It is based on experimental data and describes well MD for all of them. In particular, the behavior of topological cross sections for pure annihilation defined as the difference between topological cross sections $\sigma_n(p\bar{p})$ and $\sigma_n(pp)$ at the same energy

$$\Delta\sigma_n(p\bar{p} - pp) = \sigma_n(p\bar{p}) - \sigma_n(pp) \quad (1)$$

can be described by this model.

Experimental data indicate a double-humped structure of topological cross sections for the pure annihilation contribution [14, 15] $\Delta\sigma_n(p\bar{p} - pp)$. The subtraction of $\sigma_n(pp)$ means excluding the diffraction contribution.

The interesting experimental observations are presented in [16]. These authors indicate the absence of leading nucleons and appearance of three pionic clusters observable at that. It allows us to determine the scheme of proton-antiproton annihilation that is distinct from pp interactions.

In this report, we present the single description of MD at annihilation of leptons and hadrons with formation of newborn particles. Investigation of these processes will explain the series of data and give us understanding of strong interactions in the NP region.

2. Electron-positron annihilation

In accordance with QCD, electron-positron annihilation to hadrons is realized through gamma-quantum or Z^0 -boson creation and formation of the quark-antiquark pair. These quarks can give branchings if they have enough high energy. Three basic elementary events are possible at that: 1) bremsstrahlung by the quark and gluon ($q \rightarrow q+g$), 2) gluon fission ($g \rightarrow g+g$), and 3) production of a quark pair by a gluon ($g \rightarrow q + \bar{q}$). This quark-gluon cascade presents the first stage of MP (2)

$$e^+ + e^- \rightarrow q + \bar{q} \rightarrow (q, \bar{q}, g) \quad (2)$$

Quarks and gluons are unobservable particles, they must transform to the real hadrons. This stage is called hadronization. Its description into framework of NP QCD is difficult.

Physicists quantify multiparticle processes based on probability approach. It includes definition of the multiplicity distribution (MD), P_n and its moments. P_n is defined as the ratio of topological cross section σ_n to total inelastic σ_{in} , $P_n = \sigma_n/\sigma_{in}$. P_n is the probability to produce n secondary particles. MD calculations taking into account two stages are conveniently performed in the language of generating functions (GF). By definition, GF, $Q(s, z)$ is the sum (3):

$$Q(s, z) = \sum_n P_n z^n, \quad (3)$$

where z is the auxiliary variable, s – energy squared. MD can be easily derived from $Q(s, z)$ (3)

$$P_n = \frac{1}{n!} \frac{\partial^n}{\partial z^n} Q(s, z)|_{z=0}. \quad (4)$$

Correlated moments $F_k(s)$ are used at MP study as well

$$\begin{aligned} F_k(s) &= \overline{n(n-1)(n-2)\dots(n-k+1)} \\ &= \frac{\partial^k}{\partial z^k} Q(s, z)|_{z=1}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the horizontal bar above the expression means averaging. The average multiplicity \bar{n} , the variance D_2 (6) and the second correlated moment f_2 are by definition equal to

$$\bar{n} = \sum_n n P_n = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} Q(s, z)|_{z=1}, \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_2 &= \overline{n(n-1)} - \bar{n}^2 = Q''(s, z)|_{z=1} - (Q'(s, z)|_{z=1})^2, \\ D_2 &= f_2 + \bar{n}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

MD calculating of quarks and gluons (partons) at the first stage were derived by two groups [9, 10] independently. Our approach is based on the results of A. Giovannini [10]. He constructed a system of two differential equations for the quark (Q) and gluon (G) GFs and obtained their solutions, neglecting the formation of a quark pair by a gluon (the third elementary event).

To describe these branching processes, he introduced probabilities of two elementary events: \tilde{A} for bremsstrahlung by the quark a gluon and A for the gluon fission. He used the evolutional parameter $Y = c_1(1 + c_2 \log Q^2/\mu^2)$, where c_1 , c_2 and μ are QCD constants, Q^2 is the square of the transmitted momentum.

In accordance to [10], MD of gluons in a quark jet is the Pólya distribution. It is well known as the negative binomial distribution (NBD) (8),

$$\begin{aligned} P_m^q &= \frac{k_p(k_p+1)\dots(k_p+m-1)}{m!} \\ &\times \left(\frac{\bar{m}}{\bar{m}+k_p}\right)^m \left(\frac{k_p}{\bar{m}+k_p}\right)^{k_p}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and the Yule-Furry distribution of gluons in a gluon jet (9)

$$P_m^g = \frac{1}{\bar{m}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\bar{m}}\right)^{m-1}, \quad (9)$$

where $k_p = \tilde{A}/A$, m is the multiplicity, \bar{m} is its mean value.

The choice of MD on the second stage of e^+e^- -annihilation is based on experimental data. It is known that the second correlative moment (7) takes on negative values at low energies (see Figure 1) and it changes with increasing of energy [17]. At the same time, the second correlative moment for proton interactions changes sign at lower energies of colliding particles. It should be noted that this moment for the MD of gluons in q -jet is always positive

$$f_2^g = \frac{\bar{m}^2}{k_p} > 0.$$

We consider the hadronization stage predominant at low energy as qg -cascade and it is not enough developed yet. That is why MD at the second state has to be described by MD with negative f_2 . Among them, the Bernoulli (or binomial) distribution is the most prevailing (10)

$$P_n^h = C_{N_p}^n \left(\frac{\bar{n}_p^h}{N_p}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\bar{n}_p^h}{N_p}\right)^{N_p-n}, \quad (10)$$

where index p corresponds to q (quark) or g (gluon), $C_{N_p}^n$ is a binomial coefficient, \bar{n}_p^h and N_p are the average number of hadrons forming from single parton p and their maximum possible multiplicity at the hadronization stage.

The next necessary step is the convolution of these two stages. It is obvious that hadronization occurs without the essential of momentum transfer so called soft decoloration. In that case, GF joining qg -cascade and hadronization can be presented by the following way (11)

$$Q(s, z) = \sum_m P_m^p Q^h(m, s, z). \quad (11)$$

The ratio $\frac{\bar{n}_p^h}{N_p}$, $p = q$ or g determines the probability to create single hadron from parton

FIG. 1: Variations of correlative function f_2 with \bar{n}_- for annihilation and non-annihilation data [17].

p at the second stage. We suppose their approximate equality. It allows us to exclude gluon parameters by the auxiliary factor α . That simplification can change designations for hadronization parameters: $\bar{n}_q^h = \bar{n}^h$, $N_q = N$, $\bar{n}_g^h = \alpha \bar{n}^h$, $N_g = \alpha N$.

Using (8,10,11) we obtain MD of hadron in e^+e^- -annihilation (12)

$$P_n(s) = \Omega \sum_m P_m^p C_{(2+\alpha m)N}^n \times \left(\frac{\bar{n}^h}{N} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\bar{n}^h}{N} \right)^{(2+\alpha m)N-n}, \quad (12)$$

where Ω is the normalization factor for comparison with data. We called this convolution the two-stage model (TSM). After its modification and application to hadron interactions we called it the gluon dominance model (GDM).

The expression (12) describes experimental MD [18-25] for e^+e^- -annihilation to hadrons in

the wide energy interval from a few GeV up to 200 well [26, 27]. In Figure 2, the description of MD by TSM at 22 and 161 GeV is presented. This model demonstrates good agreement with these data [19, 24]. We applied TSM to the description of data for 18 values of energy and analysed behavior of all TSM parameters.

Dependencies of the average gluon multiplicity, \bar{m} , at the first stage and the hadronization parameter \bar{n}^h are shown in Figure 3. We describe \bar{m} by logarithmic function $\bar{m} = m_0 \log(s/s_0)$ with $m_0 = 5.67 \pm 0.02$ and $\sqrt{s_0} = 13.65 \pm 0.5$. The unexpected result demonstrates the hadronization parameter. It remains practically constant and equal to unity throughout the entire studied interval $\bar{n}^h = 0.947 \pm 0.002$.

That behavior of \bar{n}^h evidences the fragmentation mechanism of hadronization proposed by B. Mueller [28]. It is realized in vacuum when one gluon turns into single hadron.

FIG. 2: The description of experimental data [18] (left) and [24] (right) by TSM [26, 27].

FIG. 3: The average number of gluons \bar{m} and the hadronization parameter \bar{n}^h versus energy.

It is consistent with the local parton-hadron duality (LoPAD) hypothesis used previously for the transition from partonic to hadronic multiplicity.

k_p is the ratio of q -bremsstrahlung ($q \rightarrow q + g$) to g -division ($g \rightarrow g + g$): $k_p = \tilde{A}/A$. It takes values more than 1, which indicates the

predominance of bremsstrahlung over fission. It tends to decrease with increasing energy. Within the statistical bootstrap model, it was shown, k_p^{-1} can be interpreted as the "temperature" at that stage, it rises with energy.

The second correlated moment f_2 (7) can be obtained from GF by (11)

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_2 &= F_2 - F_1^2 = \sum_{m=0} (2 + \alpha m) \left(2 + \alpha m - \frac{1}{N} \right) P_m^q(\bar{n}^h)^2 - [(2 + \alpha \bar{m})\bar{n}^h]^2 \\
 &= \left[\alpha^2 \frac{\bar{m}^2}{k_p} + \alpha^2 \bar{m} - \frac{2 + \alpha \bar{m}}{N} \right] (\bar{n}^h)^2.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{13}$$

At low energy (smaller than 5 GeV) in the expression (13), TSM parameters take the following values: $\alpha < 1$, $N \approx 6$, $\bar{m} \ll 1$, and the second correlated moment becomes negative.

3. $p\bar{p}$ -annihilation

Our next step in GDM is getting the scheme for calculation of MD in the proton-antiproton annihilation. It also consists of two basic stages: quark-gluon cascade and hadronization. But unlike e^+e^- -annihilation, both, the proton and antiproton have a more complex composition, namely, three pairs of valence quark-antiquark pairs.

Also, this reaction considerably differs from proton-proton interactions. There is a clear excess of pions from $p\bar{p}$ -reaction over the corresponding proton interactions at the same energy [29]. Experiments on proton-antiproton annihilation has begun more than fifty years ago. The theory of strong interactions, QCD has not been ready to describe this reaction on the quark-gluon language. Physicists were describing the behavior of topological cross sections by the multiperipheral models.

We can mention one more difference between these two hadron reactions like occurrence of such a channel like $\bar{p}p \rightarrow (\Lambda\bar{\Lambda}) + \pi's$, which cannot occur in pp interactions [29]. In $p\bar{p}$ processes, the disappearance (absence) of leading particles is observed [30]. A particle whose vector momentum approximates to that of an incident one is called a leading particle. It is important to emphasize that this phenomenon was found out at low energies.

But the most wonderful result for understanding mechanism of $\bar{p}p$ -annihilation on our opinion is the experimental evidence “with leading pion separating across a large rapidity gap from 3π cluster, the latter decaying often into $\rho\pi$, $f\pi$, ...” [16]. In that time, the term jet was not used for a designation of a hadron cluster.

The same behavior is observed in $K^+K^- \rightarrow 2\pi^+2\pi^-$, but it starts at lower energy. There is a

similarity between $p\bar{p}$ and e^+e^- for production of resonances such as ρ^0 , f^0 and $K^*(890)$.

Twenty years ago we modified the two stage model [26, 27] to describe MD in proton interactions including high multiplicity events. This scheme got the name a gluon dominance model [6, 7, 31]. We believe that MD in $\bar{p}p$ -annihilation can be describe in that scheme of gluon branching at first stage and a universal hadronization stage. But the differences between pp interactions and $\bar{p}p$ annihilation change the initial picture before the qg -cascade.

Experimental research of pp interactions have been carried out at U-70 accelerator (IHEP, Protvino). It was suggested searching for collective phenomena in the region where multiplicity is much more than average (“Thermalization” project). 3 institutes (IHEP, JINR and SINP MSU) took active participation in that project.

We waited for manifestation of such collective phenomena as pionic jets creation, Cherenkov radiation of gluons, Bose-Einstein condensation of pions, excess of soft photon ($p < 50$ MeV/c) yield and others. The important part of our SVD-2 setup was high multiplicity trigger, which suppressed registration events with small number of secondaries. It let us register high multiplicity events, confirm manifestation of collective behavior.

Before starting “Thermalization” project, we implemented Monte Carlo simulation of pp interactions with a 70 GeV p-beam. The simulated MD underestimated data obtained at the Mirabelle bubble chamber by 3 orders of magnitude at maximum registered $n_{ch} = 18$.

In the beginning of our study, we included in our scheme of MGD all six valence quarks and antiquarks, including also several newly born active gluons. Comparison with data showed that \bar{n}^h turned out considerably less than 1 ($\bar{n}^h \approx 1$ in e^+e^- -annihilation).

A natural step would be to assume: not all 3 pairs of valence quarks are involved in the interaction (central collisions are rare). Excluding from the scheme one pair, then two pairs, still left

the value of \bar{n}^h smaller than 1.

And only the complete exclusion of all valence quarks from our scheme led to the growth of \bar{n}^h , it even has exceeded 1. That excess over unity evidences the changing of a hadronization mechanism: in e^+e^- -annihilation it is realized through fragmentation (in vacuum), in hadron and nuclear interactions through recombination mechanism (more dense qg -medium).

In that way, this means that valence quarks are staying in the leading particles. Sources of all newly born secondaries appear from active gluons. GDM describes well MD in the interval of energies from 50 GeV/c (lab system) up to 60 GeV (c.m.s.). We observed the growth of average multiplicity \bar{m} of active gluons and \bar{n}^h . One of our main experimental results evidences that more than 64% of kinetic energy, E (c.m.s.) is converted to mass of secondary pions.

Pure $\bar{p}p$ -annihilation is obtained by subtracting of pp -contribution (diffraction interaction) as it has been defined in (1). Negative value of the second correlative moment f_2 as you can see in Figure 2, right, allows us to describe hadronization by the binomial distribution.

FIG. 4: A simple scheme of valence quarks from a proton (u_1, u_2, d) and an antiproton ($\bar{u}_1, \bar{u}_2, \bar{d}$) at the beginning of annihilation. Active gluons are also presented.

GDM offers the description of $\bar{p}p$ -annihilation through the formation of three intermediate charged quark topologies with corresponding contributions c_0, c_2 and c_4 , which are stipulated by all kinds of permutations from valence quarks and antiquarks with the formation of three leading pions. In Figure 4 valence quarks

of proton are shown by blue color. At that, we differ u quarks as u_1 and u_2 , d -quark is single. We use the red color for antiproton and the same numeration for its \bar{u} quarks.

2 variants of "0"- topology ($3 \pi^0$):
 $u_1\bar{u}_1 + u_2\bar{u}_2 + d\bar{d}$ and $u_1\bar{u}_2 + u_2\bar{u}_1 + d\bar{d}$;

4 variants of "2"- topology (π^0, π^+, π^-):
 $u_1\bar{d} + u_2\bar{u}_1 + d\bar{u}_2, u_1\bar{u}_2 + u_2\bar{d} + d\bar{u}_1$
 $u_1\bar{u}_1 + u_2\bar{d} + d\bar{u}_2, \text{ and } u_1\bar{d} + u_2\bar{u}_2 + d\bar{u}_1$;

Topology "4" (and higher) is formed by adding to a valence quark (an antiquark) the corresponding antiquark (quark), which are born from active gluons ($g \rightarrow q + \bar{q}$):
 $u_1\bar{d} + \bar{u}_1d + u_2\bar{d} + d\bar{u}_2 + \dots (\pi^+, \pi^-, \pi^-, \pi^+)$;

FIG. 5: (Top) two variants of "zero"-topology (three π^0); (middle) four variants of "two"-topology (π^+, π^-, π^0); (bottom) "four"-topology.

FIG. 6: (Top) two variants of "zero"-topology (three π^0); (middle) four variants of "two"-topology (π^+, π^-, π^0); (bottom) "four"-topology.

According to experimental data and results obtained from GDM, we can form from valence quarks and antiquarks three, so-called, leading pions. The rest of secondary particles are created by active gluons. These leading pions can be

all three neutral or two charged and one π^0 . The number of both variants is determined by combinatorial permutations.

The “zero”-topology ($3\pi^0$) has only two variants (see Figure 5, top):

$$u_1\bar{u}_1 + u_2\bar{u}_2 + d\bar{d} \text{ and } u_1\bar{u}_2 + u_2\bar{u}_1 + d\bar{d}.$$

In the case of “two”-topology (π^+, π^-, π^0), the number of combinatorial permutations doubles (as it shown in Figure 5, middle):

$$u_1\bar{d} + u_2\bar{u}_1 + d\bar{u}_2, u_1\bar{u}_2 + u_2\bar{d} + d\bar{u}_1, u_1\bar{u}_1 +$$

$$u_2\bar{d} + d\bar{u}_2, \text{ and } u_1\bar{d} + u_2\bar{u}_2 + d\bar{u}_1.$$

The “four”-topology is realized when valence q (\bar{q}) catches up \bar{q} (q) formed at the decay of an active gluon ($g \rightarrow q + \bar{q}$). They are shown by green color in Figure 5, bottom. The minimum number of charged mesons in the last topology is not less than four.

Define contributions of these topologies as c_0, c_2 , and c_4 . GF for pure $\bar{p}p$ -annihilation $\Delta(\bar{p}p \rightarrow pp)$ (1)

$$Q(s, z) = c_0 \sum_m P_m^G [1 + \frac{\bar{n}^h}{N} (z - 1)] + c_2 z^2 \sum_m P_m^G [1 + \frac{\bar{n}^h}{N} (z - 1)] + c_4 z^4 \sum_m P_m^G [1 + \frac{\bar{n}^h}{N} (z - 1)]. \quad (14)$$

For comparison with experimental data [14]

we use the following expression

$$P_n = c_0 \sum_m^M \frac{\bar{m}^m e^{-\bar{m}}}{m!} C_{mN}^n \left(\frac{\bar{n}^h}{N}\right)^n \left(1 - \frac{\bar{n}^h}{N}\right)^{mN-n} + c_2 \sum_m^M \frac{\bar{m}^m e^{-\bar{m}}}{m!} C_{mN}^{n-2} \left(\frac{\bar{n}^h}{N}\right)^{n-2} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{n}^h}{N}\right)^{mN-(n-2)} + c_4 \sum_m^M \frac{\bar{m}^m e^{-\bar{m}}}{m!} C_{mN}^{n-4} \left(\frac{\bar{n}^h}{N}\right)^{n-4} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{n}^h}{N}\right)^{mN-(n-4)}. \quad (15)$$

The received values of parameters are as follows: $\bar{m} = 3.36 \pm 0.18, N = 4.01 \pm 0.61, \bar{n}^h = 1.74 \pm 0.26$. The ratios $c_0 : c_2 : c_4 = 15 : 40 : 0.05$ at $\chi^2/\text{ndf} = 5.77/4$. In the summation over m , the maximum number of active gluons $M = M_4 = 4$ is observed with topology “four”. Summation over m starts with $m = 1$ (inelastic events). The tail of high multiplicity is reached by a contribution of the “four”-topology.

Hadronization parameters coincide with values for pp interactions obtained at approximately the same energy. Ratio of possible permutations for “zero” and “two” topologies (1/2)

is close to our predicted ratio of $c_0 : c_2$ (1/2).

In accordance of data [16], the second correlative moment remains negative at $s < 30 \text{ GeV}^2$ (Figure 1). Its value increases linearly with increasing average multiplicity of negatively charged particles, n_- . The explanation of such behavior can be made in this way. Taking GF in the simplified view like $Q(z) \propto [1 + \frac{\bar{n}_-}{N_-} (z - 1)]^{mN}$, we get $f_2 = -m \frac{\bar{n}_-^h}{N_-} = \frac{\bar{n}_-}{N_-}$, where \bar{n}_- is average multiplicity of negative pions. Parameters \bar{n}_-^h and N_- varies slowly. So, f_2 changes linearly with \bar{n}_- , which is what we observe at the experiment.

With increasing energy, the multiparticle production becomes more complicated due to the gluon fission, which leads to a change in the sign of f_2 from “minus” to “plus”.

4. Conclusion

Annihilation in lepton and hadronic interactions can be described by GDM. This study started more than 30 years ago. This model is based on QCD and the phenomenological scheme of hadronization. Among the main results, we can separate an active role of gluons in multiparticle production, passive participation of valence quarks in leading particles in pp collisions they remain in initial nucleons, in opposite case, for pure $\bar{p}p$ annihilation, they form 3 pion jets.

The hadronization stage shows us that

its parameters remain constant in lepton interactions and grow slowly in hadron reactions, which evidences the changing of hadronization mechanism from fragmentation to recombination. GDM explains double-humped behavior of P_n for pure annihilation (1). GDM especially is useful for the study of events with high multiplicity.

The interesting comparison of secondary hadron creation by active gluons can be made with DNA replication when it divides into two helixes on analogy with quark-antiquark pair obtained from an active gluon.

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